

ISic1309

I.Sicily inscription 1309

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

'nel largo di Cifali, inter rudera aedis q.d. Veneris'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8745

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140801

1. [— — — — —]

2. καὶ οἱ [γονεῖς]

3. Κρισπε [ἴνος καὶ]

4. Ῥωσκ [ία — — —]

5. #⁷#⁷#⁷ [— — — —]

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492914

EDCS 39101679

PHI 140801

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0486 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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